

Coding Sample: Survey Responses (Q5)

ID	Q5: Anonymized responses	Q5: Code 1	Q5: Code 2 (optional)	Q5: Code 3 (optional)	Q5: Code 4 (optional)	Q5: Type of relationship
1	"We usually have external dependencies for which we have to wait. In case, the sprint does not have much of dependencies then its mostly delivered 90%-100% on time."	task dependencies				direct relationship (WT)
2	"Sometimes we have epics which are complex - technology or business are entirely new. In this case, we need to invest more time in SPIKE stories and we deliver less."	project newness				direct relationship (TE)
3	"We need to focus more on code quality rather than quantity. We often have to refactor code to move to PRD. This holds us back. We also need to reserve more time for testing so that our builds do not fail in production."	lack of code quality insufficient testing		bugs or incidents		direct relationship (NR) indirect relationship
4	"If tribes align more on their priorities and requests, we will have less internal dependencies and we become more predictable for our deliveries."	organizational alignment	task dependencies			contributory relationship

This overview presents a coding sample for survey question 5: "How do these factors (from Q4) influence the timeliness of epic deliveries?". Each author is allowed to assign at least one and up to four codes to each reported relationship. Intervening factors are marked in blue. In case a response reports on multiple relationships, multiple rows can be used (one row per reported relationship).